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**CULTURAL VIOLENCE PRACTICES AGAINST FEMALES IN NZANYI ETHNIC GROUP OF
MAIHA LGA, ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

While women's rights studies in Africa have grown, little attention has been given to how cultural and traditional practices contribute to the abuse of women's rights. This study focuses on cultural violence against women in the Nzanyi ethnic group of Adamawa State, using a mixed-method design with both quantitative data. Survey for the quantitative data involved 120 questionnaires administered to females from the Maiha Local Government Area of Adamawa State. The quantitative data were analysed using 5 Likert-type scales and Mean Scores Rating. The results from this research showed that various incidences of cultural violence practices against females (CVPAFs) were documented from the Nzanyi ethnic group. On the nature of CVPAFs, women are discouraged from engaging in formal jobs because they are expected to be full house wife had the highest mean score rating. The agreed factors responsible for CVPAFs are Illiteracy or low level of education, using of culture to discriminate against female and cultural beliefs to justify gender-based violence. The exclusion of women from decision making process had the highest rating on the experience and consequences of females that were affected by CVPAFs. Based on the findings from this study, it is recommended that CVPAFs is criminal in nature and can be referred to the law enforcement agencies for prosecuted as a legal mitigating measure. Culturally, there is a need for traditional ruler to enlighten and encourage the community to accord respect to female gender, embrace culture of peace based on non-violence, tolerance, allowed dialogue, mutual understanding and justice. The organization of seminar to create awareness on the effect of violence against female was agreed as part of the remedies for mitigating CVPAFs and there should be advocacy to abolish CVPAFs that are harmful to women.

Keywords: Cultural Violence, Women, Nature, Mitigation, Nzanyi

INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, gender based violence (GBV) has become a major subject of public discourse and debates in literature. Specifically, incidence of GBV against women is as old as the history of man which occurs across cultures and plays an important role in justifying itself. However, the occurrence and volatility of GBV also differ from one culture to another, depending on the traditions and cultural practice value of the people. Cultural violence against Female (CVAF) is a global phenomenon which is entrenched in many cultures such as Honour killing, Forceful feeding, Dowry custom and Breast ironing etc. In some cultures, female have been victims of honour killing (Honour killing, most often, is the murder of a female by male family members). As seen, the honor phenomenon inspires violence and honor killings. This perception exists not only in Muslim and Arab societies but is also found in Western societies such as Spain, Greece, and Italy. Honor killings

are primarily associated with countries in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), but are also rooted in other cultures. The UN estimated that 5,000 women and girls are murdered each year in honor killings, which are widely reported in the Middle East and South Asia, but they also occur in countries as varied as Brazil, Canada, Iran, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Egypt, Sweden, Syria, Uganda, United Kingdom, the United States, etc. (Honor Based Violence Awareness Network - HBVAN, 2023).

Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa, with a population of 234,192,588 million people (UN 2025), of which male population is about 118,589,884 which is 50.6% and female constitute 115,602,711 which is 49%. According to United Nation (2025), despite the fact that we are in the twenty-first century, tradition, culture, religion, and other factors have continued to widen the gender gap as women are kept in a subordinate position to men. Furthermore, in Nigeria, several instances of CVAF have been recorded, which showed that 25% of women aged between 15 and 49 years have undergone female genital mutilation/cutting (FGM/C), while 48 percent of women aged between 20 and 49 years were married before the age of 18 in the northern part of the country (Gennari *et al.*, 2014 and Garcia-Morena *et al.*, 2015). In Adamawa State, the issue of CVPAFs is also common in many traditional contexts, as reported by Dimas & Benjamin (2014). The Lala, Yungur, Honna, and Ga'anda, culturally believe that a girl must perform her cultural ritual or initiation before she can be admitted into adulthood. The ritual entails the inscription of special design marks on their body, private part, forehead, arms, and thighs to indicate that she is mature enough to get marry (Dimas & Benjamin, 2014).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Extant studies on GBV have mostly focused on domestic violence against women at their place of work, including on issues of rape of women and other discrimination against women. However, there is still little literature on cultural violence against women, especially in the northern part of Nigeria, where culture is mostly entrenched and patterns the way of life of the people. To address this gap in literature, this study examined harmful cultural violence practices against women in Nzanyi ethnic groups in Adamawa State, Nigeria. For this problem to be lingering among Nzanyi ethnic group, the women will be in total bondage and it is against the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Hence, there is an urgent need to alleviate a longtime limitation that culture had created for the women in Nzanyi ethnic group via this study.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to examine cultural violence practices against female in Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- (1) identify the nature of CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State.
- (2) identify the factors responsible for CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State.
- (3) investigate the experiences and consequences of the females affected by CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State
- (4) evaluate the various mechanisms used for mitigation CVPAF among the selected ethnic groups in Adamawa State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the nature of CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?
2. What are the factors responsible for CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?
3. What are the experiences of the female affected by CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?

4. What are the various mechanisms used for mitigating CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

Feminist theory represents the expansion of feminism into theoretical, philosophical, and literary discourse, aiming to understand gender disparities. Radical critics argue that the rights-based approach presumes an existing equality, which reflects and sustains gender dominance. Radical feminist theory frames social relations through gender-based oppression. It encompasses interdisciplinary research in anthropology, sociology, economics, women's studies, and literary criticism (Zajko & Leonard, 2006; Howe & Aguiar, 2001; Pollock, 2007). Feminist theory analyzes gender politics, power structures, and sexuality to explain inequality, as shown by Bracker and Brown (1997) and Penny and Nicola (2001). Its goal is to promote women's rights while reviewing existing social and political structures. Feminist theory addresses issues like discrimination, stereotyping, objectification (especially sexual), oppression, and patriarchy. Literary critic Elaine Showalter (1989) identifies three phases in feminist ideology: “feminist critique,” which analyzes texts through a feminist lens; “gynocriticism,” in which women create textual meaning; and “gender theory,” which explores how ideology and literature shape the sex/gender system. Over time, diverse feminist movements and theories have emerged. The traditional “Big Three” models—liberal, radical, and socialist/Marxist feminism—have expanded into newer forms (Maynard, 1995). Some feminisms align with wider political ideologies, while others focus on specific issues like the environment.

Liberal feminism originates from seventeenth- and eighteenth-century political theorists like Locke and Rousseau, who emphasized equality and natural rights. Since Wollstonecraft (1752), liberal feminists have argued for equal legal rights, full citizenship, and access to education and employment. Modern liberal feminists reject some classical ideas like rigid individualism and the public-private divide (Okin, 1989), while advocating for legal and social reforms to ensure women’s equality. Liberal feminists have worked with groups like the National Organization for Women to address sexism and educational gender bias. Though limited in scope, liberal feminism has expanded women's access to higher education, employment, and reproductive rights. Its assumptions underlie much of social science research on gender inequality. The phrase “radical feminism” emerged in the U.S. during the 1960s to describe views asserting that women’s oppression is systemic (Jaggar & Rothenberg, 1984). Radical feminists argue that male dominance underpins gender relations and call for dismantling patriarchy, not reforming it.

Radical feminists focus heavily on how male control over women’s bodies perpetuates inequality, especially through rape, abuse, and control of reproduction. Radical feminist theory includes two major strands: Socialist feminism, rooted in Marxist theory, emphasizes the material and economic bases of women’s oppression. Unlike liberals, Marxists argue that equal opportunity cannot exist in class-based societies. Socialist feminists like Mitchell (1971) stress the role of social class and show how capitalism and patriarchy combine to subjugate women (Rubin, 1975). Marxist theory appeals to feminists for its emphasis on power, oppression, and historical context. It promotes revolutionary change and links theory to political practice. Marxist ideas also stress the necessity of historical and comparative analyses, internally inconsistent social formations, and dialectical as opposed to linear causality. Marxists have also consistently emphasized the significance of dramatic social change and the link between theory and political practice. Socialist feminists have drawn on these perspectives while updating Marxist traditions to make women's subordination and gender relations more central. Most prefer this word to acknowledge a tradition far wider than Karl Marx's works.

Conceptual Framework

Cultural Violence Against Females (CVAF) is a widespread global phenomenon embedded in various cultures. Forms include honor killing, forced feeding, dowry practices, and breast ironing. Honor killing—typically, the murder of a woman by male relatives—is one manifestation. This practice, rooted in notions of shame and family honor, exists not only in Muslim and Arab societies but also in parts of Western Europe like Spain, Greece, and Italy. While honor killings are commonly associated with the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), they occur in diverse settings. The UN estimates that 5,000 women and girls are killed annually for reasons tied to honor, with cases reported across countries like Brazil, Canada, Iran, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Egypt, Uganda, Sweden, the UK, and the US (HBVAN, 2023). In such societies, honor is a supreme value. Religious doctrines, particularly Islam, shape cultural understandings of honor and shame, often justifying violence as a response to perceived disgrace (Dogan, 2011). Perpetrators typically claim that victims tarnished family reputation (Douglas & Raghu, 2009).

Review of related empirical studies

Cultural norms evolve slowly over time punishments per se may not be enough if society does not contemporaneously act to change dysfunctional social norms. The recommendation is that a privileged channel is education, communicating positively through the media and through modern social networks seems another promising avenue which is in similar vein with the report of Regina and Patrick (2011) who investigated a study on cultural violence and the Nigerian women. They explore the cultural factors responsible for violence against women and the negative effects of cultural violence against women in Nigeria. The study made a case for raising public consciousness against it. Violence against Women or Gender-Based Violence is an age long psychological and social issue deep-rooted in Nigerian societies and African countries in general. In some societies, cultural practices, norms and beliefs fuel the behaviours and relegate women to second-class status. Some practices and gender role assignments ensure total submission of the woman to male dominance and control at home in a way that perpetuates gender inequality. The data for this research were derived from the primary and secondary sources and both descriptive and analytical methods were used to assess the impact of cultural violence on women. The previous study was based on Cultural Roots of Violence against Women Individuals in some countries and Cultural factors contributing to gender-based violence in Zambia whereas the present study is on cultural violence and Nigerian women. The study demonstrates that cultural violence against women manifested in all levels of socio-cultural, economic, and political status of women in Nigeria irrespective of class, education or profession. The research reveals that in Nigeria, gender preference culturally favours the male child to continue the family name, entitles him to land and property ownership, to visit and talk with the elders where older women only cook and serve the men at family or community meetings. The results suggest that the acceptance or rejection of violence against women is deeply rooted in ancestral social norms of different ethnic groups. These social norms persist even when economic and social conditions evolve, and may affect many generations. The results show that violence behaviours are deeply rooted in ancestral socio-economic conditions. It also warned us against disappointments from quick solutions. Finally, the study recommended that they should be certified and qualified Community psychologists, Community service Social Workers and Case Managers who are very familiar with the clients' tribal characteristics such as dialect, customs, attitudes and other related features.

METHODOLOGY

The study area is Adamawa State which is located in the Northeast geo-political zone of Nigeria. The State was created in August 1991 from the defunct Gongola State and occupies about 38,000 square kilometres with a population of 4,902,100 (City Population 2022). The state capital is Yola and there are 21 LGAs in the State (Figure 1). Adamawa State is bordered by Borno to the northwest, Gombe to the west and Taraba to the southwest. Nzanyi people are an ethnic group located in the northeastern part of Nigeria particularly in Adamawa State as well as the neighbouring countries such as Cameroon. They are the majority in Maiha LGA of Adamawa State. The language is a Chadic language with traditional practices and customs unique to this ethnic group. The major occupation of the people is farming; the cash crops are cotton and groundnut while the food crops are maize, yam, cassava, guinea corn, millet, and rice while some engaged in cattle herding. (Adamawa State Planning Commission, 2022).

Figure 1: Map of Adamawa State showing the study Area

Research Design

This study adopted the quantitative research design which provided the overall framework for collecting data. The quantitative approaches to balance out the limitation of each method and provide stronger evidence and engender confidence in the findings (MacMillan and Schumacher, 2001). Durrheim (2004) reported that research method is a strategic framework for action that serves as a bridge between research questions and the execution, or implementation of the research strategy, the use of this design becomes pertinent because an in-depth description and interpretation of cultural violence practices especially against female was generated. Structured questionnaires were used to determine the opinion of respondents.

Population of the Study

The population of this study were females, 120 structural questionnaires were administered to them. The Local Government Areas is from the Northern Senatorial zones of Adamawa State for this study Maiha Local Government Area with the population of 196,900. Three communities (Pakka Humbutudu and Vakumna) were selected from Maiha Local Government Area where 40 questionnaires were administered to the females in each of the communities, making a total of One hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study focused Nzanyi Ethnic group in Maiha LGA of Adamawa State. Random sampling technique was used for this study. The research areas and respondents were randomly selected to have a total sample of 120 persons for quantitative administration of questionnaires. Three communities were selected and at each of the communities 40 questionnaires were administered making a total of 120 questionnaires for each Local Government area. Each of the participants' consent was sought before administering the questionnaire for ethical purpose.

Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection for this study was structured questionnaire (SQ) and divided into five sections. The respondent's opinions were expressed on 5 point Likert type scale using: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D). The respondents indicated their respond to each of the items by ticking one option of their choice. The concepts of the study were explained to the respondents and those that could not read and write were assisted with interpretation in their local languages and filling of the questionnaires.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The validity of the questionnaire that was used in gathering data for this study were assessed and ascertained by some of lecturers from the Centre for Peace and Security Studies and a lecturer from the Department of Technology Education. The reliability of each of the items and subjective options were necessary and subjected to reliability test in other to ensure the possibility of achieving the objectives of this research. This was done by experts in the Department of Statistics and Operational Research, Modibbo Adama University, Yola using Kronbach $\alpha = 0.965$.

Method of Data Collection

After securing the consent of the authority of each community the researcher explained the importance of the research and the need for their cooperation in assisting to administer the questionnaires to the respondents. The instruments used for data collection were structured questionnaire administered to the respondents using kobo collect for filling their responses.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected through questionnaires were sorted using Microsoft Excel Package. Data representation was done with Tables Mean Score values.

Calculation of Mean Score Values:

Using the midpoint of Strongly Agree 5+Agree 4+ Undecided 3+ Disagree 2+Strongly Disagree 1/5 = 3 Using three as midpoint for Agree and Disagree. Any point below 3 is disagree and any point above 3 is agree.

RESULTS

1. What is the nature of CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?

Table 1. Nature of Cultural Violence Practice Against Females in Nzanyi Ethnic Group

S/No	QUESTION	SA	A	U	D	SD	Cal. Mean Score value	Decision
1	Female education among the Nzanyi ethnic group is highly discouraged	81	33	2	4	0	4.59	Agree
2	Nzanyi culture encourages and promotes early marriage among the females	82	36	0	1	1	4.64	Agree
3	Women are forced into early marriage	68	43	4	4	1	4.44	Agree
4	Women are discouraged from engaging in formal jobs because they are expected to be full house wife	95	23	0	1	1	4.75	Agree
5	Nzanyi woman is expected to depend on her husband for house all up-keep and other expenses	83	30	4	3	0	4.61	Agree
6	More preferences are given to male than female children in the Nzanyi culture	86	30	2	2	0	4.67	Agree
7	Women are denied the opportunity of enjoying socio-economic rights like men	88	27	5	0	0	4.69	Agree
8	Given birth to female children by a Nzanyi woman can make the husband to divorce her or marry additional wife	85	28	2	3	2	4.59	Agree
9	Barren women are treated with discontent and their husbands have the option of divorcing them or marrying additional wife	74	31	4	6	5	4.36	Agree

The table showed that Females in the NNzanyi ethnic group are discouraged from engaging into formal jobs because they are expected to be full house wife as this recorded highest MSV of 4.75. The females are denied opportunity to enjoy socio-economic rights had the second largest MSV with 4.69 which is followed by more preferences are given to a male than female child. The nature of the cultural violence against female among the Nzanyi ethnic group was that barren women are treated with discontent and their husbands have the option of divorcing them or marrying an additional wife was rated the lowest among other nature.

2. What are the factors responsible for CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?

Table 2. Factors Responsible for CVAF among the Nzanyi Ethnic Group in Adamawa State

S/NO	QUESTIONS	SA	A	U	D	SD	Cal. MeanScore value	Decision
1	Economic benefits associated to cultural practices that discriminates against women	58	39	8	10	5	4.13	Agree
2	Stigmatization of the female gender	56	38	8	12	6	4.05	Agree
3	Cultural believe systems of the people	53	42	8	11	6	4.04	Agree
4	Manipulation of culture against the female gender	55	37	7	13	8	3.98	Agree

5	Illiteracy or low level of education of some of the people that use culture to discriminate against women	64	38	5	6	7	4.21	Agree
6	Abuse of culture as a tool of discrimination	54	39	9	11	7	4.02	Agree
7	The accepted use of culture as a strategy of revenge for settling scores	58	40	6	9	7	4.11	Agree
8	Culture is also used as a tool of bargaining	59	38	7	8	8	4.10	Agree

The nine (8) identified factors responsible for CVAF among the selected ethnic groups in Adamawa State on (Table 2) were all accepted by the respondents because their MSV were greater than 3.0. Illiteracy or low level of education of some the people that use culture to discriminate against women was rated with the highest MSV of 4.21, which is followed by MSV 4.13 Economic benefits associated to cultural practices that discriminates against women and the lowest MSV of 3.98 showed that women are being manipulation of by men.

3. What are the experiences of the female affected by CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?

Table 3. The experience and consequences of female that were affected by CVAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa state

S/No		SA	A	U	D	SD	Cal. Mean Score	Decision
1	Shame	57	42	9	7	5	4.16	Agree
2	Discrimination	59	41	8	8	4	4.19	Agree
3	Depression	61	38	8	9	4	4.19	Agree
4	Psychological trauma	39	36	13	11	21	3.51	Agree
5	Sexually transmitted diseases	50	36	11	14	9	3.87	Agree
6	Isolated lifestyle	49	35	11	17	7	3.82	Agree
7	Exclusion from decision making process	69	37	4	8	2	4.36	Agree
8	Mental illness	31	30	14	21	24	3.19	Agree
9	Loss of livelihood	48	32	8	8	24	3.60	Agree
10	Isolation	48	33	9	10	20	3.66	Agree
11	Drug Abuse	50	31	10	10	19	3.69	Agree

The indices on the understand the experience and consequences of female that were affected by CVPAF among the selected ethnic groups were all accepted although the highest MSV (4.36) was recorded on the index that women are excluded from decision making process followed by women are discrimination and depression with MSV of 4.19 and the lowest MSV 3.19 was accepted by the respondent that women suffer from mental illness (Table 3.).

4. What are the various mechanisms used for mitigating CVPAF among the Nzanyi ethnic group in Adamawa State?

Table 4. Remedies for mitigating CAVFs among the Nzanyi ethnic groups in Adamawa state

S/No	Items	SA	A	U	D	S D	Cal. Mean Score value	Decision
1	Culture-based violations against female that are criminal in nature can be referred to the law enforcement agencies for prosecution.	61	39	7	5	8	4.17	Agree
2	Legal punishments may be given to perpetrators of cultural-based violence against female victims.	47	48	13	5	7	4.03	Agree
3	Perpetuators of cultural-based violence can be arrested and if guilty forced to pay compensation to the female victims.	50	41	14	7	8	3.98	Agree
4	We should embrace culture of peace based on nonviolence, tolerance, dialogue, mutual understanding and justice.	64	45	2	4	5	4.33	Agree
5	The traditional rulers have roles to play in enlighten and encouraging the community to respect female gender.	68	38	4	5	5	4.33	Agree
6	Creating awareness by organizing seminar to reduce the level of violence against women.	63	44	4	5	4	4.31	Agree
7	Psycho-social/Counseling support service to assist female victims of cultural violence.	61	45	5	5	4	4.28	Agree
8	Ministry of women affairs in collaboration with British Council and United women to help the survivor of CVPAFs economic empowerment opportunities (Skills acquisition or financial interventions)	60	47	4	4	5	4.28	Agree
9	Compensation for survivors of CVPAFs	51	45	13	5	6	4.08	Agree
10	Repudiation and punishment of perpetrators of CVPAFs	40	49	20	4	7	3.93	Agree
11	Create protective community healthy physical and social environment to reduce CVPAFs	58	50	3	4	5	4.27	Agree
12	Provide quality education to the community so as to reduce risk of CVPAFs	64	45	2	4	4	4.34	Agree

The questionnaire showed the remedies use for mitigation CVPAF among the selected ethnic groups using all the twelve (12) items were accepted. The highest ranked was that Provide quality education to the community so as to reduce risk of CVPAFs with MSV of 4.34 which showed that remedy is more acceptable in mitigating cultural violence practice against female followed by they should embrace culture of peace based on nonviolence, tolerance, dialogue, mutual understanding and justice and The traditional rulers have roles to play in enlighten and encouraging the community to respect female gender (MSV 4.33) while the lowest MSV 3.93 was recorded for the Repudiation and punishment of perpetrators of CVPAFs (Table 4)

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The nature of cultural violence among the Nzanyi ethnic group shows that due to its special relationship with other cultural institutions, ideas, and aspirations, gender is a significant factor in determining social stratification and inequality (Ofoegbu, 2015) although among the Nzanyi, the female gender has been denied. This subordinate position of women among the Nzanyi is an act of violence since the United Nations General Assembly (2015) stated that violence is also used to maintain

and enforce the subordinate position of women. The United Nations and its member nations condemn domestic abuse as one of the "crucial social mechanisms by which women are driven into subordinate [positions] compared with males" in the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women.

Understanding the experience and consequence of cultural violence against females, the report of Anbacha and Kjosavik (2019) on consequences of CVPAF agreed with all these which include Smoking, drug abuse, anger, agitation, hostility, distrust, violent acts, theft to mention a few. The implication is that the violence acts will lead to social vice that will have long term effect on both the immediate community and globally.

Among the various mechanism in mitigating cultural violence against female, there is no simple or single solution to the problem; rather, violence must be addressed on multiple levels and in multiple sectors of society simultaneously (WHO, 2002). The remedies will proffer solution as adequate measures to combat CVPAF in the communities and ethnic groups studied. One could see that there is a need to investigate allegations of GBV thoroughly and effectively, prosecute and punish those responsible, and provide adequate protection, care, treatment and support to victims/survivors, including access to legal counseling, health care, psycho-social support, rehabilitation and compensation for the harm suffered. Measure to eliminate all beliefs and practices that discriminate against women or sanction violence and abuse, including any cultural, social, religious, economic and legal practices must be taken as documented by Sebastian and Kerstin (2020) while drastic action to empower women and strengthen their personal, legal, social and economic independence must be taken.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion all forms of cultural violence practices that are harmful and injurious to women at any level of their development should be discarded since culture is a way of life which is dynamic; one does not expect it to be destructive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government roles in advocating and enforcing girl child education is essential and penalty can be imposed on people that do otherwise.
2. The traditional institution needs advocacy within the community while the state ministry of women affairs needs to intervene through workshop to interact with the adherent of these cultures in Adamawa state and let them know the evil it is bringing to the community and need to adjust, knowing that it is a long term belief of the people and cannot be easily eradicated

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